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Review Article

**A REVIEW ARTICLE ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN
PHARMACEUTICALS AND HEALTHCARE****Rashmi Kate*, Dr. Ganesh Deshmukh, Sanjana Patil, Adiksha Mishra,
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Navi Mumbai-400705, Maharashtra, India**Article Received:** July 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:**

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a branch of computer science that deals with problem solving task with help of symbolic programming. Artificial Intelligence (AI) mimics the human cognitive functions. It brings about a model shift in the healthcare field as it can be applied to various types of healthcare data. Majorly cancer, neurology and cardiology are the disease state in which AI tools works. AI techniques include machine learning, deep learning etc. AI in pharmaceuticals can reduce the time required for drug development which in turn will reduce the cost of its development. AI can tackle many challenges like lack of medical profession. Many leading IT companies are working to collaborate with this AI in order to sustain the position and wellbeing of human healthcare.

Keywords: Algorithms, data mining, artificial neural network, NITI aayog.

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INTRODUCTION:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is an area of computer science that includes development of computer system which are able to perform tasks normally requiring human intelligence and emphasizes the creation of intelligent machines that work and react like humans. AI is used to describe the property of machines and program. It uses algorithm and software which approximates human perception in analysis of compound medical data. AI can be differentiated with traditional technologies as AI has the ability to gain information, process it and then giving well defined output [1,2].

AI does this through machine learning and deep learning algorithms. These algorithms have the ability to recognize the patterns in behaviour and then it creates its own logic. Now in order to reduce the margin of error these algorithms need to be tested or calibrated regularly or rather repeatedly. AI have been developed and applied to practices such as diagnosis processes, developing treatment protocol, drug development, protocols for clinical trial, personalized medicines and patient monitoring etc. [2].

AI in healthcare is the approximation of human cognition and analytical abilities using algorithms and software. It includes [2,3]

- Analysis of complex medical data.
- Prognosis, diagnosis, prevention of disease state.
- Storage and mining of huge medical electronic records.
- Assist in market research and medical surveys.

RATIONALE AND NEED OF AI IN PHARMACEUTICALS AND HEALTHCARE In Pharmaceuticals:

While considering the pharmaceutical industry, recognizing that tedious tasks in pharmaceutical are generally associated with large amounts of data, so it becomes clear that AI and industries could collaborate. As the manufacturing plants operate on computerized or programmable logic-controlled machines or technologies within fixed operating procedures to produce products of standard quality, compatibility towards highly automated and robotic machineries is evident. Now through integration with AI self-learning machines compound operations can be simplified to greater extent [4].

The various reasons behind incorporating AI in pharmaceutical industry can be enlisted as follows [4]:

- Huge amount of drug data being generated and utilized per year which needs to be analysed regularly to obtain useful information out of it.

- Various new compounds, NCE (New Chemical Entity) and molecules are screened for discovery of new compounds and potential drug sources.
- Screening of long strands of DNA sequence, millions of genes and genomes of various species will help understand the genomics of various species and their evolutionary relationships.
- Sources and impacts of mutations of proteins and genes could be easily detected using AI-aided software which is practically impossible for the molecular biologist and geneticist.
- Millions of formulations are manufactured on a large scale in various pharmaceutical companies. Maintaining their consistency, quality and uniformity in the production of pharmaceuticals in a shorter span of time is of paramount importance for the companies and thus AI would be helping them to achieve it.
- There is a huge dearth of expertise, highly skilled pharmaceutical technicians and manpower to carry out cumbersome tasks of pharmaceutical fields in various developing countries and thus AI can help them bridge this gap.
- Clinical decision making is a critical step in any clinical trial or research project and thus intelligent software having the abilities to analyze, evaluate and give conclusions based on the clinical data would help us to overcome the various hurdles in decision making in the clinical trials of various medicines.

In Healthcare:

There is a huge disparity in the number of doctors and medical professionals in our country and the number of patients in need of health service. There has been an uneven ratio of skilled doctors to patients in our nation for a long time post-independence. 4.8 practicing doctors per 10,000 population (Indian journal of public health, 2017 edition), which is expected to grow to 6.9 per 10,000 people by the year 2030, while the minimum doctor to patient ratio recommended by WHO is 1:1000.

Also, for increasing effective disease diagnosis at an early stage and reduce the numbers of misdiagnosis or delayed diagnosis of the patients AI could prove to be an efficient and indispensable tool [5].

AI is an effective measure to tackle challenges like:

- Lack of medical professionals.

- Making doctors more skilled at their jobs, training doctors and nurses to tackle complex procedures.
- Providing high-quality healthcare to rural areas.
- Connecting professionals from different parts of the globe.

CURRENT GLOBAL SCENARIO AND STATISTICS

Figure 01: Major areas in healthcare using AI [3]

The following statistics shows the major area of healthcare using artificial intelligence respectively for cancer, nervous and cardiac disorder. The growth of global AI in healthcare field is driven by the ability to improve patient outcomes, increase in adoption of precision medicine, need to increase coordination between healthcare workforce and patients and notable rise in capital investments.

CURRENT SCENARIO OF AI: INDIA AND WORLD

India:

India, being the fastest growing economy with second largest population in the world, has a significant stake in the AI revolution. Acknowledging AI's potential in transforming economics and its need in India so Hon'ble finance minister in his budget speech 2018-2019 sanction NITI Aayog to initiate national program on AI in order to guide research and development in the stream of novel and boosting technologies. NITI Aayog has patterned with several leading AI companies to implement AI projects in critical areas of healthcare.

Early detection of diabetic retinopathy is a pilot project on which NITI Aayog is working with Microsoft and Forus health under the campaign of #AIFORALL. This campaign will aim at strengthening and empowering human capabilities to authorize the challenges to access, scarcity, affordability and inconsistency of skilled expertise.

#AIForALL will focus on harnessing collaborations and partnerships [6].

World:

The following are examples of large companies that have contributed to AI algorithms for use in healthcare [4]

IBM

At Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Centre and Cleveland Clinic IBM Watson Oncology are in development. IBM is additionally working with CVS Health on AI applications in chronic disease treatment and with Johnson & Johnson on analysis of scientific papers to seek out new connections for drug development.

Microsoft

Microsoft's Hanover project, in partnership with Oregon Health & Science University's Knight Cancer Institute, analyses medical research to predict the foremost effective antineoplastic treatment options for patients. Other projects include medical image analysis of tumor progression and therefore the development of programmable cells.

Google

Google's Deep Mind platform is being used by the UK National Health Service to detect certain health risks through data collected via a mobile app. For detecting cancerous tissues, a second project with the NHS was taken which involves analysis of

medical images collected from patients in order to develop computer vision algorithm.

Start-ups

IDx's first solution, IDx-DR founded by Michael Abramoff, is that the first and only FDA authorized AI system for the autonomous detection of diabetic retinopathy. As an autonomous, AI-based system, IDx-DR is exclusive therein it makes an assessment without the necessity for a clinician to also interpret the image or results, making it usable by health care providers who might not normally be involved in eye care. IDx may be a leading AI diagnostics company on a mission to rework the standard, accessibility, and affordability of healthcare worldwide.

Other software applications

Infermedica's free mobile application Symptomate is that the top-rated symptom checker in Google Play. The company also released the primary AI-based voice assistant symptom checker for 3 major voice platforms: Amazon Alexa, Microsoft

Used for decision making in:

Product formulation
PK-PD studies

Drug QSAR modelling
Protein structure/function prediction

Cortana, and Google Assistant. Digital consultant apps like Babylon Health's GP at Hand, Ada Health, and Your.MD use AI to offer medical consultation supported personal medical record and customary medical knowledge. Users report their symptoms into the app, which uses speech recognition to match against a database of illnesses. Babylon then offers a recommended action, taking under consideration the user's medical record.

APPLICATIONS

Pharmaceutics:

1. Artificial neural network:

A computer system modelled based on the human brain [7]. Uses multilevel probabilistic analysis, which allows computers to simulate the data processing of the human mind and give an output based on weighted inputs in various pharmaceutical settings [8]. Works similar to the functions of neuron (single level perceptron) but has multiple inputs (multi-level perceptron) to give one single output [9,10].

Figure 02. An illustration of artificial neural networks (ANN)

a. Application of ANN in pharmaceutical drug product development:

An immediate release tablet formulation of anhydrous caffeine modelled on ANN. Two networks were developed, one comprising five inputs diluent type, diluent level, binder level, granulation equipment used and binder addition (wet or dry) The other comprising nine inputs (the five above plus granule size, flow, bulk- and tapped-densities). Both had four outputs (tablet strength, friability, thickness and disintegration time) Both predicted results more successfully than those models generated by statistical techniques [11-13].

b. Application in Quantitative structure-property relationship (QSPR) and molecular modelling:

Developing drugs with best possible structure with maximum activity- long tedious task. ANN trained with various physicochemical descriptors; molecular connectivity helps to model QSAR to develop analogues with maximum activity in short time [14].

E.g. Out of various analogues of capsaicin, the model identified correctly 34/41 inactive compounds and 58/60 active compounds, Aqueous solubility, Human intestinal absorption, Drug presence in breast milk [15,16].

c. Protein function and structure prediction:

Used for gene identification to protein structure prediction and sequence classification [14]. Extremely useful as a structural similarity may represent an evolutionary relationship that is undetectable by sequence analysis [17]. Used in sequence alignment and assembly for both RNA and DNA molecules [18,19]. Determining the folding and secondary structure of RNA strands [20].

d. PK-PD Studies:

Useful when insufficient data is available to determine the PK-PD of a drug or which drug will have a desired effect for an individual patient [8]. Predict PK/PD profiles accurately for a wide variety of PK-PD relationships [14]. PD profile can be accurately predicted without any need of information of the active metabolite [21].

2. Drug synthesis/design:

Two approaches [8]: 1) search through the huge database of similar molecules,

2) use library of fragments and join them together.

Improved search algorithms, evaluation of large databases of chemical structures can be performed to guide the design of novel molecules with appropriate properties [22,23]. AI can be used to reduce the number of potentially useful molecules to controllable numbers of possibly lead compounds [24-26]. AI may help in drug target identification and validation; target-based, phenotypic, and multi target drug discoveries and biomarker identification [27,28].

3. Clinical Trials:

Takes an average of 12 years for a drug to go from the research lab to the patient. Only five in 5,000 pre-clinical testing to human testing. For human usage out of these five is ever approved. On average, it costs a company US \$359 million to develop a new drug from the research lab to the patient. Identify molecules that have failed in clinical trials and predict these same compounds for targeting other diseases [29]. Cross-compare massive sets of data from past trials to find similarities and patterns. Take operational performance from historical trials and predict the probabilities of success or failure in a protocol design [30]. Electronic medical records to cross-reference hundreds of available trials based on specific criteria. Lead to increased efficiency, more effective time estimates and lower costs [31].

Healthcare:**1. Disease diagnosis:**

AI-powered image recognition can also be used to identify and classify medical images to reach more accurate diagnoses [32]. E.g. To recognize lesions and nodules; localize organs, regions, etc. Finding diabetes by looking at retinal images, detecting

anomalies in heart activity or detecting tumor development at an early stage [33].

a) Echocardiography

The Ultramics system, trailed at John Radcliffe Hospital in Oxford, uses AI to analyze Echocardiography scans that detect patterns of heartbeats and diagnose coronary heart disease [34-36].

b) Screening for neurological conditions

AI tools are developed to analyze speech patterns to predict psychotic episodes [3]. Identify and monitor symptoms of neurological conditions such as Parkinson's disease [37].

c) Radiology and imaging

AI may aid clinicians in detecting a minute change, augment the workflow of radiologists and pathologists, acting as clinical decision support and enhancing care delivery [38]. A study at Stanford created an algorithm that can detect pneumonia better than radiologists. The FDA recently cleared an AI algorithm that can detect distal radius fractures and provide clinical decision support at the point of care [39].

d) Wearable machines and devices

A continuous glucose monitor (CGM) is a diabetes device that is inserted and worn under the skin for a specified number of days [40]. Can read record glucose readings every few minutes for both type 1 and type 2 diabetes. Better glucose control, improved quality of life. Comprises of 3 parts: sensor, transmitter, receiver [41].

2. Telemedicine and consultation:

Includes AI- aided chatbots, for diagnosis and recording symptoms video, voice, text consultation with doctors and medical experts [42]. Important in rural areas having lack of medical professionals and experts [43].

3. Electronic health records:

Maintain large volumes of health and medical data. Helps in data mining and processing. Used for huge comparative studies and surveys [44].

4. Assisted surgeries:

Micro-surgical procedures require precision and accuracy. Assist physicians reduce variations in procedures [45]. Compensate for the differences in the skills of physicians in cases of new or difficult surgeries [46].

5. Medication management:

AiCure app was used to monitor the patient use of medication which was created by the National Institutes of Health. A smartphone's webcam combined with AI, can confirm that patients are taking their prescriptions and help them manage their condition [47]. People with serious medical conditions, patients who tend to go against doctor

advice, and participants in clinical trials benefit from this [48].

6. Virtual nurses:

AI has developed Molly, a digital nurse to help people monitor patient's condition and follow up with treatments, between doctor visits [4]. The program uses machine learning to support patients, specializing in chronic illnesses and to answer patient's questions and help reduce unnecessary hospital visits [49].

LIMITATIONS AND SOLUTIONS

Limitations:

- No-One-Size-Fits all solution.
- Security and technical glitches may lead to damage, data loss, breach of privacy.
- Potential of automation technology leading to job losses.
- Cost and Maintenance of technology.
- Change and acceptance by patients.
- Approval and regulatory control.

Solutions:

- Making customized solutions and being patient centric.
- Development of software and better tools, analytics and privacy policies.
- Training and deployment of skilled personnel for handling AI software's and machines.
- Large scale development and use of AI.
- Building public trust and reliability.
- Regulation of the software and laying guidelines & specifications.

FUTURE

The transformation of healthcare using AI will gradually occur over the next 10 or 20 years. AI is expected to be integrated into most, pharmaceutical R&D operations, improve the drug development success rate and streamline R&D efforts[11]. AI may help accurately identify the subset of patients who will benefit from a particular drug. Reduce the failure rate substantially and ensure a successful launch [14]. Encouraging collaborations between the industry and academia, and between medical and engineering faculties at universities. Medical schools could include an AI elective in their curriculum and fellowship programs focusing on AI could be created. Governments can help by investing in the development of AI infrastructures. Once all stakeholders develop a deeper understanding of AI and partnerships are strengthened, patient care and outcomes will ultimately improve [50].

CONCLUSION:

Along with big data, AI is doubtless the next big thing for pharmaceutical and healthcare sector. It will be more advantageous to those company who will inculcate the AI faster. Implementing AI will soon be necessary to compete in the industry and

sustain for a longer period of time. In order for AI to positively impact patients and healthcare professional's pharmaceutical companies needs to become invested in advantages of AI technology. The way we experience the process of the healthcare from diagnosis of disease to post-operative procedures will change fundamentally. AI will strengthen us in dealing with chronic diseases of cardiovascular system, metabolic disorders, and deadly diseases like cancer.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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